

Ergonomic Recommendations for the Home Office

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ABSTRACT: In this article, we analyse the ergonomic set-up of the Home Office (HO), and summarize recommendations as found in current online literature. The first section outlines the transition towards the Home Office and its current key numbers and particularities. The second section presents workers' ergonomic preferences and HO practices. The majority underlines the ergonomic importance of HO equipment such as a second screen, a dedicated HO room, or a sit/stand-desk. Corporal practices during Work-From-Home (WFH) include, for example, walking in the garden or breathing exercises.

KEYWORDS: Home Office (HO), Working From Home (WFH), Ergonomics, Human Body, New Work

The Home Office: Past, Present, and Future Tendencies

In the past, working was defined by being physically present at the location of your company. With the progress of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and pushed by the COVID-19 crisis, working remotely became possible and with it, the progressive emergence of diverse ways of working remotely. This led to divers' transformations of work organisation. The practice of working remotely from home began on a small scale in the 1970s. But only in the 1980s, the emergence of the Internet and its associated technologies had been enablers for new ways of working remotely. Those enablers led to a growing practice of working remotely in the 2000s, mainly from home with personal devices. In 2017, this practice reached a significant level with 25% of French employees working regularly from home. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-2021 had been the catalyst for the massive adoption of this new working model, also named "Working-From-Home" (WFH). The highest level for WFH was reached with the COVID pandemic peak in 2020, with 41% of French employees working remotely at home. Since 2022, this mode stabilized around 36% as it became a standard way of working. Many variations appear, including full remote mode (Barrero, Bloom & Davis, 2024; Cicek, 2024). The adoption of working remotely is changing the working patterns, the organizations, the management modes, including the information systems supporting them, but also the relationships towards work. The reactions of companies concerning WFH is ambiguous or even ambivalent. Some companies imposed a partial return of workers in company premises for improving efficiency and team building. Others propose a full remote mode for some employees. Managers are facing a new situation concerning work control, coordination and team management. WFH is proposed to improve flexibility, productivity, and a better quality of life. It has the potential to increase the work-life balance. To do so, an adequate level of WFH needs to be applied facing the particularities of each position and its context. At the same time, only certain jobs can be realised from home, whereas other workers don't have this option - e.g. in the heavy manufacturing or healthcare sector. WFH represents implications concerning work organisation & management, productivity and efficiency, required IT infrastructure and equipment, regulation and company responsibilities, protection of employees and psycho-social risks, etc. Many of those impacts are subject to studies by various organizations, including companies themselves, but with different levels of progress.

Facing those impacts, many companies, in different sectors and for different types of jobs, issued some specific guidelines for regulating remote work, even if working remotely is already adopted. Those guidelines include: a maximum number of days working remotely, some mandatory on-site days, some limitations on the place for remote working, etc. Some companies in the US – e.g. Google in June 2023 – decided to go back to a typical on-site work. Google justifies it for favouring team cohesion and collaborative work. Accordingly, a strict control based on tracking office badge attendance is set, confronting workers who aren't coming in when they're supposed to and including the attendance in employees' performance reviews (Loughlin, 2023). In 2023, full-remote applies only for 4% of workers in France. As an intermediate conclusion, WFH is largely developed but divided in different modes, each with its own specificities, advantages and disadvantages (e.g. regular-, occasional-, hybrid telework, full remote, or coworking). This article will focus on the most typical mode of working remotely as it is currently operated in France. The upcoming section will present the ergonomic recommendations for a comfortable and efficient WFH environment and indicate current tendencies and best practices. The following sections describe the minimum requirements for a WFH environment, set for

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comfort, productivity but also safety and data security. The second part will focus on the link between the ergonomic WFH set-up and productivity / creativity.

Connectivity is the key aspect allowing an efficient and comfortable WFH environment. New communication technologies with optical fiber, 5G network and even satellite connexion with their higher bandwidth make interactions (audio & video) seamless and allow meetings with numerous participants, whatever their location. Therefore, WFH is requiring an adapted IT infrastructure for protecting data and preventing intrusion, with the use of technologies like VPN, encryption, authentication (2FA, PKI, MFA, biometric, or OTP). IT infrastructure needs to be upgraded towards emerging threats, including a permanent monitoring of network activity and the regular training of employees related to data security and cybersecurity. WFH requires a workstation, powerful enough for supporting multiple communication and collaborative software (MS Teams, Zoom, etc.). Productivity software is required for time management, pdf tools, image management, etc. Accordingly, common recommendations for WFH workstations are the following: A laptop with a lid of 15-17 inches offering a comfortable surface of display and adapted for mobility, an adequate weight (less than 2 kg is recommended) easing transport between home and office, enough processing capacity, RAM for a good reactivity concerning software execution and a generous hard drive storage for all pieces of software and data production & storage, full connectivity interface (Ethernet, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth) for wired or wireless connexions and data transfer, optionally, the use of a security device for identification, authentication and data encryption/decryption (Dongle, Authentication card, Biometry, etc.). As many interactions are to be done, some additional hardware needs to be considered: An external display to ease the use of many pieces of software at the same time or to display different sources of information, a comfortable mouse and keyboard (even wireless), and comfortable headsets for attending meetings. Just as in the company office, the general environment is also important. The following points are to be considered for a pleasant and efficient WFH environment: A dedicated workspace, such as an office or table separated from the rest of the home, An ergonomic chair, making your posture safer, without head or back pains, a table or desktop for the installation of your hardware but also your personal items (stickers, bloc note, agenda, workbooks, pencils etc.), lightning for your visual comfort (Including an anti-reflection filter for screens), and air conditioning for a room with a pleasant temperature to allow a continuous level of concentration.

Currently we witness certain WFH ambivalences: The need for more days of working remotely expressed by employees, up to switching to full remote, facing the limitations of working remotely imposed by companies up to promoting a return to a 100% face-to-face work mode. Nevertheless, working remotely such as with hybrid work is considered a social acquis. One point highlighting this is that 50% of French employees are ready to consider a job change in case of a return to face-to-face work every day. Computers have gained more capability since the 80's. But Human-Machine-Interfaces (HMI's) remain largely the same as in the 80's, the age of first computers, with a "WIMP" interface (Windows, Icons, Menus, Pointer). HMIs should allow the user to perform tasks with minimal effort and confusion. Therefore, psychology enters HMI conception, as understanding the cognitive processes of users is crucial in designing HMI's. Cognitive ergonomics seeks to optimize interfaces according to the capabilities and limitations of information processing by the human brain. Colours, shapes, animations or sound feedback should be thought of according to their cognitive impacts. The following technologies are under active development and will modify in depth our interactions with computers and the opportunity of more efficient work: Delivering immersive experiences, these technologies are profoundly changing the way we interact with digital information. With devices such as VR (Virtual Reality) headsets and AR (Augmented Reality) glasses, the boundaries between real and virtual are becoming increasingly blurred. Systems like Leap Motion or Kinect have highlighted the possibility of controlling interfaces by natural hand or body gestures without direct physical contact. With the integration of AI, HMI's become able to understand context, predict user needs and adapt to individual preferences. Using voice as a means of interaction has become commonplace thanks to personal assistants such as Siri, Google Assistant, and Alexa. Voice recognition allows for more natural communication with devices. Some Artificial Intelligence with a voice recognition are now available in a standalone way but their integration in software could lead for productivity improvements due to more seamless interactions. At the forefront of HMI research, these interfaces aim to create a direct communication between the brain and the computer, eliminating the need for physical devices. For the moment, Neuralink is in an early stage of development with only two persons paired with an implant in November 2024. Their potential impact on WFH remains under evaluation. In 2024, the emergence of IA has revolutionized our interactions with our computers. An on-going trend is the integration of IA in software and operating systems, for discharging users of some tasks or accompanying them in some others, intensifying our relationship with IT environments.

Ergonomic Recommendations

The current ergonomic standards and recommendations for WFH are designed to promote comfort, efficiency, and overall well-being, which is particularly important as more people work from home. To optimize the home office setup, there are several key ergonomic guidelines and best practices to consider. It starts with the office chair, which is essential to ensure that its height is adjustable, allowing people to sit with the feet flat on the ground, thighs parallel to the floor, and knees bent at a 90-degree angle. Proper lumbar support is also crucial for maintaining the natural curve of the spine and reducing strain. Additionally, adjustable armrests should allow the elbows to rest comfortably at a 90-degree angle while typing. The chair's seat depth must be suitable,

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allowing people to sit fully back with a gap of 2-4 inches (5 to 10 centimetres) between the back of the knees and the edge of the seat. The height of the desk should be set so that the forearms remain parallel to the ground or slightly inclined while typing. Adequate leg space under the desk is also vital to ensure comfort and promote circulation. The screen should be positioned at eye level and placed about an arm's length away to minimize neck and eye strain. If people are using multiple monitors, the primary screen should be directly in front of you with the secondary one positioned to the side to reduce unnecessary neck twisting. Furthermore, it is important to adjust the screen to avoid glare from windows or overhead lighting. Concerning the keyboard and mouse setup, wrists should be kept straight and hands at or slightly below elbow level to avoid strain. Wrist rests can provide additional support if necessary. The keyboard should be directly in front of the person, and the mouse placed within easy reach to prevent overextending the arm. Lighting also plays a key role in creating an ergonomic workspace. Natural lighting enhances concentration in the long-term. If needed, people can use task lighting for specific activities, but it should not cause glare or shadows on the workspace. Maintaining a good posture is essential as well. People need to sit upright with the back fully supported by the chair, avoiding slouching by using lumbar support or a cushion to help maintain the spine's natural curve. In addition to proper posture, taking regular breaks is key to preventing musculoskeletal issues. Aiming to take short breaks every 30 to 60 minutes to stand up, stretch, and move around, is beneficial. Following the 20-20-20 rule—looking at something 20 feet away for 20 seconds every 20 minutes—can reduce eye strain.

Other ergonomic accessories, such as a footrest, monitor riser, or document holder, can help maintain optimal body positioning. If people spend a lot of time on calls, using a headset or speakerphone can prevent strain from cradling a phone between the ear and shoulder. The temperature and air quality in your workspace also affect comfort. The room should be at a comfortable temperature, ideally between 19 and 23°C, with sufficient ventilation to ensure proper air circulation. Lastly, personalizing the setup to fit individual needs is crucial, as ergonomic solutions should be customized based on body dimensions and preferences. Regularly assessing comfort and adjusting as needed is key to maintaining long-term success in WFH environment.

In conclusion, the main goal of ergonomic recommendations is to enhance comfort, prevent strain or injury, and boost productivity. For most jobs, the ergonomic requirements remain consistent: a good office chair, a proper desk, a well-positioned computer screen, a keyboard and mouse, appropriate lighting, good posture, frequent breaks, a comfortable working environment, and reliable internet and power backup to prevent interruptions.

The ergonomic HO setup impacts well-being, productivity, and creativity by aligning the workspace with the body's natural posture and movement, reducing discomfort, and minimizing the risk of injury. A well-designed HO that follows ergonomic principles enhances well-being in many ways, while also influencing creativity through the physical environment, creating a setup that fosters mental flexibility and openness to innovative ideas. Proper chair support, desk height and monitor and keyboard placement reduce strain on the back, neck, eyes, and wrists, preventing musculoskeletal disorders and chronic pain, which helps to maintain both physical and mental health. Moreover, reducing physical discomfort can lower stress levels, leading to a calm and focused environment that improves mental well-being by reducing anxiety related to prolonged sitting, eye strain, and repetitive motions. When the workspace supports healthy posture and movement, it conserves energy, enhances concentration and sustains energy levels, which boosts productivity. Additionally, minimizing physical strain frees up mental resources for problem-solving and innovative thinking, creating a functional environment that supports cognitive functioning. An ergonomic workspace also fosters "flow", a state of deep focus and engagement that enhances creative output (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990).

Comfort plays a key role here, as physical ease leads to positive moods linked with greater creativity, and ergonomic setups that promote movement, like sit-stand desks, further stimulate creativity by encouraging physical activity, which can improve cognitive flexibility. However, certain factors can hinder productivity and creativity in a HO setting. The absence of structure may make time management challenging, leading to disorganization, which stifles creativity. Common household distractions, such as chores, pets, and social media, disrupt focus and make it difficult to achieve a flow state. Isolation from colleagues can reduce the collaborative energy needed to spark creative ideas, while working in a familiar environment might stifle creativity by providing too much comfort. Monotony, stemming from repetitive routines, can also dull creative thinking, and technical issues or inadequate tools can frustrate the creative process. Moreover, blurred boundaries between work and personal life can lead to burnout, reducing both motivation and creative energy, while overworking at home often results in fatigue, further hindering creativity. A HO setup that prioritizes ergonomics can enhance well-being by reducing discomfort and promoting both physical and mental health. At the same time, it creates an environment that fosters creativity by supporting cognitive functioning, improving focus and enhancing mood. On the other hand, challenges can also be raised via HO, so addressing those potential challenges like distractions, isolation and work-life imbalance requires establishing boundaries, creating a conducive work environment and maintaining a healthy balance between work and relaxation.

Barrero, Bloom & Davis (2024) highlight three types of employees regarding the way of working: "fully on site", "hybrid" and "full WFH", specifying that in 2024, 62.2% of employees were fully on site. In their study it appears that some specific sectors are more likely to be done on site: Hospitality & Food services, Retail Trade, transportation and Warehousing, Manufacturing, Education, Construction, Government, Health and social assistance (Barrero, Bloom & Davis ; 2024). Furthermore, we witness temporal evolutions throughout the career. Before Covid-19, some employees were always fully remote and remained this way, some were

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fully presential and went back to it, some went fully remote and are now in hybrid mode. For those in hybrid mode this poses certain challenges. In meetings, there can be unequal participation modalities, which also lead therefore to unequal social interactions. Therefore, some prefer to ban hybrid working modes, focusing entirely on presence (as for example Google). Creative professions show a higher tendency to be physically present. This is linked to the material particularities of artistic practices – e.g. the importance of tools and materials.

An advantage of the HO is avoiding the time and costs of travelling between Home and the workplace. The Covid-19 crisis and its impact on the HO-transition cannot be underestimated. Covid-19 served as a technologic accelerator, heavily promoting digital tools and solutions (e.g. for online meetings). Some of which were difficult to implement before the pandemic became widespread standards because of the Covid-19 pandemic. Still, a certain type of meetings is preferred to be held in person. Especially meetings with delicate information, concerning conflicts, intimate topics, creative tasks, or Get-to-know-meetings. The emerged remote/hybrid situation creates new communication practices between colleagues, with diverse consequences. Some insist for example in virtual coffee breaks. Some insist on physical meetings at the beginning of a project (kick-off, etc). Some employees express missing the physical collaboration with colleagues – for example when working in front of a whiteboard. For creative tasks, presence was repeatedly stated as important. The role of the human body was underlined for corporal onboarding exercises and icebreakers at the beginning of meetings showing a holistic corporal approach throughout their project management (see Embodiment - Niedenthal, 2007). Some develop individual ergonomic techniques (caressing the cat, walking in the house or in the garden), others apply existing ones (e.g. la technique de Pomodoro, Yoga techniques, breathing exercises, or power napping). Major differences in considering the human body can be differentiated according to the sector, the type of project, and the individual. Some consider the human body not at all. Other regularly. Others on a punctual basis - according to the needs of each project. Few managers present specific methods aiming explicitly at mobilising the human body. Many work practices are realized without a notable consideration of corporal aspects. Some consider the human body explicitly, others implicitly, others not, others punctually.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented the emergence and current landscape of the HO. We described the most important ergonomic necessities for WFH as found via desk research in current online literature. We identified a variety of WFH practices, according to the sector, the company, the position, and each project. The major findings of the desk research were based on Gallagher et al., 2023; Barrero, Bloom & Davis, 2024; Cicek, 2024; Rech, 2024; Yablonski, 2024. Some take the human body into account for icebreaker and onboarding functions. Others do not consider it at all. The importance of physical presence was underlined for certain types of meetings – those with sensible content, creative meetings, or project kick-offs. The rising importance of WFH requires more research on the sensorial, affective, and ergonomic implications of the Home Office. With upcoming research, we intend to do so.

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